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COMPLEXITY AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME

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ANNOTATION

The article presents the data of a clinical examination of 80 patients treated in the surgical department from 2017 to 2023. To determine the incidence of postcholecystectomy reflux gastritis (PCE RG), the total number of patients diagnosed with gallstone disease (GSD) admitted during this period was 571 people (100%). Of these, 160 patients (27.8%) sought treatment with symptoms of postcholecystectomy syndrome (PCES), while 48 (45.7%) of them were diagnosed with RG, and 50 patients (17%) required exclusively surgical correction. Patients (n=80) were divided into three groups: two main and one control. The first group (n=35) included patients with PCE RG who underwent laparoscopic or traditional surgery with correction of RG. The second group included 17 patients with gallstone disease (GSD) and RG who underwent prophylactic correction of RG during cholecystectomy (CE) to prevent the development of PCE RG. The control group (n=28) consisted of patients with PCE RG for whom a retrospective analysis of medical records was performed to identify the causes of PCE RG development.

Key words: postcholecystectomy syndrome, postcholecystectomy reflux gastritis, gallstone disease.

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СЛОЖНОСТЬ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОСТХОЛЕЦИСТЭКТОМИЧЕСКОГО СИНДРОМА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье приведены данные клинического обследования 80 пациентов, проходивших лечение в хирургическом отделении с 2017 по 2023 годы. Для определения частоты возникновения постхолецистэктомического рефлюкс-гастрита (ПХЭ РГ) было установлено общее количество пациентов с диагнозом желчнокаменной болезни (ЖКБ), поступивших за этот период – 571 человек (100%). Из них 160 пациентов (27,8%) обратились с симптомами постхолецистэктомического синдрома (ПХЭС), при этом у 48 (45,7%) из них был диагностирован РГ, а 50 пациентов (17%) потребовали исключительно хирургической коррекции. Пациенты (n=80) были разделены на три группы: две основные и одна контрольная. В первую группу (n=35) вошли пациенты с ПХЭ РГ, которым была проведена лапароскопическая или традиционная операция с коррекцией РГ. Во вторую группу вошли 17 пациентов с ЖКБ и РГ, которым во время холецистэктомии (ХЭ) была проведена профилактическая коррекция РГ для предотвращения развития ПХЭ РГ. Контрольная группа (n=28) состояла из пациентов с ПХЭС, для которых был проведен ретроспективный анализ медицинских карт для выяснения причин развития ПХЭ РГ.

Ключевые слова: постхолецистэктомический синдром, постхолецистэктомический рефлюкс-гастрит, желчнокаменная болезнь.

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POSTXOLETSISTEKTOMIK SINDROMNI XIRURGIK DAVOLASHNING MURAKKABLIGI VA XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada 2017 yildan 2023 yilgacha jarrohlik bo'limida davolangan 80 bemorning klinik tekshiruv ma'lumotlari keltirilgan. Postxoletsistektomik refluks gastrit (PXE RG) bilan kasallanish darajasini aniqlash uchun ushbu davrda O't tosh kasalligi (O'TK) tashxisi qo'yilgan bemorlarning umumiy soni aniqlandi - 571 kishi (100%). Ulardan 160 nafar (27,8%) bemorda postxoletsistektomik sindrom (PXES) belgilari bilan murojaat qilgan bo'lsa, ularning 48 nafarida (45,7%) RG tashxisi qo'yilgan va 50 bemorda (17%) faqat jarrohlik yo'li bilan tuzatish talab qilingan. Bemorlar (n = 80) uchta guruhga bo'lingan: ikkita asosiy va bitta nazorat. Birinchi guruh (n = 35) PXE RG bilan kasallangan bemorlarni o'z ichiga olgan bo'lib, RG laparoskopik yoki an'anaviy jarrohlik yo'li bilan tuzatilgan. Ikkinchi guruhga xoletsistektomiya (XE) paytida PXE RG rivojlanishining oldini olish uchun profilaktik korreksiya qilingan O'TK va RG bilan og'rigan 17 bemor kiritilgan. Nazorat guruhi (n=28) PXES bilan kasallangan bemorlardan iborat bo'lib, ular uchun PXE RG rivojlanishining sabablarini aniqlash uchun tibbiy ma'lumotlarning retrospektiv tahlili o'tkazildi.

Kalit so'zlar: postxoletsistektomik sindrom, postxoletsistektomik refluks gastrit, o't tosh kasalligi.

Kirish. O't tosh kasalligi (O'TK) oshqozon-ichak traktining eng keng tarqalgan patologiyalaridan biri bo'lib, mehnatga layoqatli aholining 10-30% ga ta'sir qiladi. So'nggi yigirma yil ichida laparoskopik xoletsistektomiya (LXE) minimal xarajat tufayli O'TK jarrohlik davolashda minimal travmatik, kasalxonaga yotqizish va rehabilitatsiya davrini qisqartirishi tufayli "oltin standart" bo'ldi.

Biroq, operatsiyadan keyingi bemorlarning hayot sifati LXE samaradorligining muhim mezon bo'lib qolmoqda. LXE jarrohlik amaliyotiga kiritilganidan 25 yil o'tib, jarrohlik davolash har

doim ham O'TK tufayli yuzaga kelgan murakkab patofiziologik o'zgarishlarni bartaraf etmasligi aniq bo'lib qolmoqda. To'g'ri bajarilgan xoletsistektomiya takroriy operatsiyalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni oldini oladi, ammo doimiy yoki davriy dori terapiyasini istisno qilmaydi.

Afsuski, o't pufagini olib tashlash har doim ham bemorning barcha muammolarini hal qilmaydi. Ba'zi bemorlarda postxoletsistektomiya sindromi (PXES) deb nomlanuvchi og'riq va dispepsiya davom etmoqda. Ko'plab tadqiqotlar va nashrlarga qaramay, O'TK kasalligini davolash muammosi dolzarbligicha qolmoqda. Operatsiyadan keyingi davrda bemorlarning 8-87% og'riq va dispeptik kasalliklarga duch keladi. PXES rivojlanishiga nafaqat umumiy o't yo'llari va katta o'n ikki barmoqli ichak papillasining patologiyasi, balki O'TK kasalligi bilan og'riq bemorlarda oshqozon va o'n ikki barmoqli ichakning motor-evakuatsiya buzilishlarining etarli darajada tashxis qo'yilmaganligi ham yordam beradi.

PXES diagnostikasi va davolashi terapevtlar, gastroenterologlar va jarrohlar uchun dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi. Jarrohlar, operatsiyadan keyingi shikoyatlar operatsiyadan oldingi tekshiruv va tuzatishning yetarli emasligidan kelib chiqadi deb hisoblashadi. PXES bilan og'riq bemorlarning 30% takroriy jarrohlik aralashuvni talab qiladi. PXESning asosiy sabablaridan biri reflyuksli gastritni o'z vaqtida tashxislash va tuzatmaslikdir, bu uzoq muddatli operatsiyadan keyingi davrda postxoletsistektomiyadan keyin reflyuksli gastrit bilan murakkablashadi. Mavjud adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish postxoletsistektomiyadan keyingi reflyuks gastritining oldini olish va davolash bo'yicha tadqiqotlar yetishmasligini ko'rsatadi.

Shu nuqtai nazardan, postxoletsistektomiya reflyuksli gastritni jarrohlik tuzatish va oldini olishning yangi usullarini ishlab chiqish uchun ushbu tadqiqot asosdir.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi postxoletsistektomik sindrom bo'lgan bemorlarda reflyuksli gastritni videolaparoskopik tuzatish samaradorligini o'rganish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. Tadqiqot 2017 yildan 2023 yilgacha jarrohlik bo'limida davolangan 80 nafar bemorning klinik ma'lumotlarini tahlil qilishga asoslangan. Xoletsistektomiyadan keyingi reflyuksli gastrit (PXE RG) bilan kasallanish darajasini aniqlash uchun ushbu davrda qabul qilingan o't tosh kasalligi (O'TK) tashxisi qo'yilgan bemorlarning umumiy soni 571 kishini (100%) tashkil etdi. Ulardan 160 nafar (27,8%) bemorda postxoletsistektomik sindrom (PXES) belgilari bo'lgan bo'lsa, ularning 48 nafarida (45,7%) RG qayd etilgan va 50 nafar (17%) bemorlarda esa faqat jarrohlik tuzatishni talab qildi.

Bemorlar (n=80) uchta guruhga bo'lindi: ikkita asosiy va bitta nazoratli. Birinchi guruhga (n = 35) RG tuzatish bilan laparoskopik yoki an'anaviy jarrohlik o'tkazilgan PXE RG bo'lgan bemorlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ikkinchi guruhga PXE RG rivojlanishining oldini olish uchun xoletsistektomiya (XE) paytida RGni profilaktik tuzatishdan o'tgan O'TK va RG bilan og'riq 17 nafar bemorni o'z ichiga oldi. Nazoratli guruhi (n=28) PXES bilan kasallangan bemorlardan iborat bo'lib, ular uchun PXE RG rivojlanishining sabablarini aniqlash uchun tibbiy ma'lumotlarning retrospektiv tahlili o'tkazildi.

PXE RG bilan og'riq bemorlar orasida 9 (25%) erkaklar va 26 (75%) ayollar, yoshi 36 dan 75 yoshgacha bo'lgan. PXE RG bilan og'riq bemorlarning aksariyati mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi (37 yoshdan 50 yoshgacha) va 66% (n = 23) ni tashkil qiladi. Birinchi guruh bemorlari ilgari O'TK uchun operatsiya qilingan va xoletsistektomiyadan keyin turli vaqtlarda kasalxonaga yotqizilgan.

Birinchi guruhdagi bemorlar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan so'rovdan so'ng, ularning 58 foizi xoletsistektomiyadan (XE) keyin sog'lig'ida yaxshilanishni sezmagani ma'lum bo'ldi. Ushbu bemorlarda davriy og'riqlar, asosan epigastral mintaqada, ko'ngil aynishi, ba'zida qusishga aylangan. Qolgan 42% dastlab o'zini yaxshi his qildi, ammo vaqt o'tishi bilan ahvoli yomonlashdi va kasallik rivojlanishni boshladi. Barcha bemorlar qayta-qayta turli mutaxassislariga murojaat qilishgan yoki o'z-o'zini davolash bilan shug'ullanishgan, bu esa faqat qisqa muddatli yengillik keltirgan.

Klinikaga yotqizilgandan so'ng, asosiy kuzatuvlar bemorlarning 87 foizida (n=31) kuzatildi. Ulardan 82% (n=29) epigastral sohadagi og'riqlardan, 16% (1-8) chap qovurg'a yoyi ostidagi, 30% (n=15) o'ng qovurg'a yoyi ostidagi og'riqlardan shikoyat qilgan.

Bemorlarning bir qismi, shuningdek, ko'ngil aynish (76%, n=27), zarda bo'lish (48%, n=17), kekirish (36%, n=13), qusish (22%, n=11) va og'izda achchiq ta'mga (25%, n=9) shikoyat qilgan. Barcha tekshirilgan bemorlarda ishtahaning kamayishi, umumiy zaiflik va charchoq shikoyatlari

mavjud edi. Kompleks tekshiruvdan so'ng, reflyuksli gastrit (RG) rivojlanishining asosiy sababi pilorik sfinkterning yetishmovchiligi (24%, n=8) va o'n ikki barmoqli ichak tutilishi (O'BIT), ham mexanik (65%, n=23) va ham funksional (18% n=6) ekanligi aniqlandi.

O'BIT ning mexanik sabablari orasida: proksimal (n=2), distal (n=3) va umumiy (n=5) periduodent, o'n ikki barmoqli ichak-jejunal birikmaning yuqori fiksatsiyasi (n=13), shuningdek, arteriomezenterik siqilish (n=3), yuqori tutqich arteriyasi va aorta o'rtasida o'n ikki barmoqli ichakning ko'tarilgan qismini siqishdan kelib chiqadi. Funksional sabablardan 4 nafar bemorda O'BIT ning gipotonik shakli, 5 nafarida gipertonik shakli aniqlangan. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, pilorik sfinkter yetishmovchiligi bo'lgan 4 nafar bemorda O'BIT ning mexanik shakli ham duodeno-jejunal birikmaning yuqori fiksatsiyasi shaklida tashxis qo'yilgan. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, birinchi va ikkinchi guruhdagi bemorlarda to'liq tekshiruv nafaqat gepatopankreatobiliar tizimning patologiyalarini, balki asosiy kasallikning kechishini murakkablashtiradigan boshqa tizimlarning kasalliklarini ham aniqladi. Pankreatit ko'pincha ikkala guruhda ham tashxis qo'yilgan: birinchi guruhdagi 13 bemorda va ikkinchi guruhdagi 9 bemorda. Birinchi guruhda birga keladigan patologiyalar orasida xoledoxolitiaz va tashqi qorin bo'shlig'i churralari ustunlik qildi, mos ravishda 9 va 8 bemorda aniqlandi. Shuningdek, 7 nafar bemorda reflyuks ezofagit, 5 nafarida umumiy o't yo'llarining terminal stenoz, 6 nafarida yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, 1 nafarida jigar sirrozi, 3 nafarida qandli diabet, 2 nafarida oshqozon yarasi aniqlangan. 8 (53,6%) bemorlarda sanab o'tilgan ikki yoki undan ortiq kasalliklarning kombinatsiyasi mavjud. Ikkinchi guruhda ko'pincha umumiy o't yo'lining terminal qismining xoledoxolitiaz va stenoz tashxisi qo'yilgan (n=10).

Bemorlar operatsiya oldidan to'liq tekshiruvdan va tegishli tayyorgarlikdan so'ng operatsiyaga olib borildi. Operatsiyaning tabiati va darajasi keyingi bo'limda batafsil tavsiflangan tadqiqot davomida aniqlangan reflyuksli gastrit (RG) va birga keladigan patologiyalarning rivojlanish sabablariga bog'liq edi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, operatsiyadan oldingi va keyingi davrda bemorlar yallig'lanish jarayonlarini kamaytirishga qaratilgan kompleks konservativ davolash oldilar.

Klinikaga yotqizilgan barcha bemorlar keng qamrovli klinik va laboratoriya instrumental tahlildan o'tkazildi. barcha bemorlar qayta-qayta turli mutaxassislariga murojaat qilishgan yoki o'z-o'zini davolash bilan shug'ullanishgan, bu esa faqat qisqa muddatli yengillik keltirgan.

Klinikaga yotqizilgan barcha bemorlar keng qamrovli klinik, laboratoriya va instrumental tahlildan o'tkazildi. Bemorlarning shikoyatlari sinchiklab o'rganilib, kasallik tarixi sinchiklab yig'ildi. Umumiy tekshiruv, qorin bo'shlig'ini tekshirish, palpatsiya, perkussiya va auskultatsiya kabi klinik tekshiruvlar o'tkazildi. Bemorlarga obzor ko'krak qafasi rentgenogrammasi, elektrokardiogramma (EKG), kardiologning maslahati va qorin bo'shlig'i a'zolarining ultratovush tekshiruvi o'tkazildi. Reflyuksli gastrit (RG) diagnostikasi uchun maxsus tadqiqot usullari qo'llanilgan, masalan, yuqori tutqich arteriyasining (YuTA) doppler ultratovush tekshiruvi, ezofagogastroduodenoskopiya (EGDFS), polipozitsion rentgen kontrastini tekshirish, me'da shirasida safro kislotalarini aniqlash, oshqozon sekretsiyasi va kislotaliligini o'rganish, diagnostika helikobakterioz va kerak bo'lganda endoskopik retrograd xolangiopankreatografiya (ERXP).

Oldingi devor bo'ylab pilorik sfinkterning etishmovchiligi, subkompensatsiyalangan bosqichdagi funksional surunkali o'n ikki barmoqli ichak tutilishi (SO'BIT) yoki yuqori turgan o'n ikki barmoqli ichak-jejunal birikma tufayli kelib chiqqan mexanik SO'BIT tufayli reflyuksli gastrit (RG) paydo bo'lgan hollarda, laparoskopik tuzatish afzallik beriladi.

Birinchi va ikkinchi guruhdagi bemorlar operatsiyadan oldingi tayyorgarlikdan so'ng turli xil operatsiyalarni o'tkazdilar, ularning turi RG ning aniqlangan sabablariga bog'liq edi. Operatsiyalar aniqlangan patologiyani tuzatishga qaratilgan. RGni bartaraf etishdan tashqari, jarrohlik aralashuvni talab qiladigan boshqa aniqlangan patologiyalar ham tuzatildi. Yakuniy tashxisni o'rnatganimizdan so'ng, biz minimal invaziv usullardan foydalangan holda RG ni tuzatishga harakat qildik. RG jarrohlik davolashda yaxshi natijalarga erishish uchun, turli tuzatish usullari, ularning ba'zilari takomillashtirilgan.

Birgalikda RG bo'lgan beshta bemor xoledoxolitiaz va umumiy o't yo'lining terminal qismining stenoz, birinchi bosqichda toshlarni olib tashlash bilan endoskopik papillosfinkterotomiya (EPST), ikkinchi bosqichda esa RGni tuzatish amalga oshirildi. Birinchi bosqichdan ikki kun o'tgach,

yopiq laparoskopik piloroplastika va duodenojejunal birikmaning qisqarishi bilan Treitz boylamining laparoskopik diseksiyonu amalga oshirildi (1-rasm).

Rasm 1. Yopiq laparoskopik piloroplastikani bajarish jarayoni (A). Operatsiyadan keyingi umumiy ko'rinish (B)

O'n ikki barmoqli ichak tutashuvining yuqori joylashuvi natijasida kelib chiqqan xolelitiyoz va oshqozon-ichak trakti bilan og'rigan uchta bemorga ham xoledoxolitiyaz va umumiy o't yo'lining terminal qismining stenozini tashxisi qo'yilgan. Bunday hollarda terminal umumiy o't yo'lining stenozini birinchi navbatda endoskopik papillosfinkterotomiya (EPST) va toshni olib tashlash orqali tuzatildi. Keyin o't pufagi va uning tarkibidagi toshlar laparoskopik usulda olib tashlandi. Shundan so'ng, Treitz boylami ajratildi va duodenojejunal birikma qisqartirildi (2-rasm).

Rasm 2. Endovideojarrohlik xoletsistektomiyasi va Treitz boylamining diseksiyasi bilan birgalikda Dormia savatidan foydalangan holda toshlarning litoekstraksiyasi bilan EPST.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Postxoletsistektomiya sindromi bo'lgan bemorlarda ochiq yoki laparoskopik usulda xoletsistektomiya (XE) o'tkazilgandan so'ng, turli darajadagi og'irlikdagi reflyuksli gastrit (RG) 45,9% hollarda yuzaga kelgan. Ulardan RG bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 17% faqat jarrohlik tuzatishni talab qildi. 24% hollarda RG rivojlanishining sababi pilorik sfinkterning yetishmovchiligi va 76% da o'n ikki barmoqli ichakning o'tkazuvchanligining surunkali buzilishi (funktional yoki organik).

Xoletsistektomiyadan keyingi reflyuksli gastritning bevosita sabablari O'TK bilan og'rigan bemorlarni dastlabki davolash va kasalxonaga yotqizish paytida to'liq tekshiruvdan o'tkazmaslik, xoletsistektomiyani amalga oshirish uchun oqilona usul va foydalanish imkoniyatining yo'qligi, oshqozon va o'n ikki barmoqli ichakni to'liq intraoperativ tekshiruvdan o'tkazishdan bosh tortish, xoletsistektomiya, shuningdek, xoletsistektomiya paytida RGni tuzatish bo'yicha kombinatsiyalangan operatsiyalarni bajarish tajribasiga ega bo'lmagan yosh mutaxassislar tomonidan xoletsistektomiyani bajarish. Ultratovush, fibroezophagogastroduodenoskopiya kabi usullarni kontrast moddan

foydalangan holda rentgen tekshiruv, shuningdek, safro kislotalari tarkibi uchun me'da shirasini o'rganish kabi usullardan foydalanish muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Postxolelitsistektomiyadan keyin reflyuksli gastritni videolaparoskopik tuzatish bilan bemorlarning 93,7 foizida a'lo va yaxshi natijalar, 4,2 foizida qoniqarli, 2,1 foizida qoniqarsiz natijalarga erishildi.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, biz tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan va takomillashtirilgan PXES bilan og'rigan bemorlarga videolaparoskopik antireflyuks aralashuvi usuli juda samarali bo'lib, bu operatsiyaning bevosita va uzoq muddatli natijalarini yaxshilash imkonini beradi.

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